

BaNb₂O₆ at Room Temperature by Ball Milling Method: Structural, Optical, Morphology, and Electrochemistry Properties

José Fábio de Lima Nascimento,* Yurimiler Leyet Ruiz, Otoniel da Cunha Mendes, Francisco Marcos Costa Batista, Andreu Cabot, José Milton Elias de Matos, Robson Dantas Ferreira, Marcus Valério Botelho do Nascimento, Libertalamar Bilhalva Saraiva, João Nazareno Nonato Quaresma, and Francisco Xavier Nobre*

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ABSTRACT: Materials that depend on high temperature, pressure, or long periods of crystallization in the obtention of the pure phase have been the focus of several studies due to the economic and ecological aspects. The high-energy ball milling method (HEBM) has been adopted to synthesize different materials using solid-state reactions. In this study, bare barium niobate was efficiently synthesized at room temperature using the HEBM. The materials synthesized at different synthesis times were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Rietveld refinement, which confirms the orthorhombic structure for BaNb₂O₆, with a high crystallinity degree at 3 h (BaNb₃) and 4 h (BaNb₄) of synthesis. The main vibrational modes of the structure were identified by Raman spectroscopy. In contrast, band-gap values between 3.77 and 3.84 eV were obtained by diffuse reflectance spectroscopy for the samples BaNb₃ and BaNb₄, respectively. The electrochemical experiments using the modified glassy carbon electrode (GCE) with BaNb₃ sample as a working electrode show the almost reversible profile for the cyclic voltammetry curves in potassium ferrocyanide in the scanning speed range of 1 to 100 mV s⁻¹. Moreover, the flat band energy (E_{fb}) indicates the *p*-type semiconductor characteristic for BaNb₂O₆, and a specific capacitance of 3375.66 mF cm⁻², suggesting an interesting material for composition *n-p* heterojunctions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The transition of fossil fuels to new sources of energy, reinforced mainly by the environmental impacts caused by pollutants derived from the use of petroleum derivatives, has been reported in several studies in the past decade, as well as research related to the efficient and safe storage of these new energy matrices.¹ At the same time, the concern with the levels of pollutants in the environment, especially persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and heavy metals has resulted in a significant number of scientific publications.^{2–4}

In this context, the semiconductors exhibit specific and promisor properties that are key to the development of new technologies in the most diverse fields of science.^{5–7} In the study carried out by Li et al.,⁸ the sensor based on the Sn₃O₄/CdS heterojunction proved efficient and reproducible in analyzing glucose in human blood and detecting Cu²⁺ ions in an aqueous medium. On the other hand, Tong et al.⁹ reports the capacitive properties of the Co₃O₄@NiMoO₄ composite, which resulted in a specific capacitance of 600 C/g under a current density of 1 A/g.

Considering the excellent properties exhibited by materials that crystallize in perovskite-like structures, especially in applications related to energy storage, remediation of organic pollutants and optical devices, it is noted that the synthesis

methods, effect of doping elements and composition of crystalline phases are factors that directly influence the desired performance of these systems.^{10–13} Among the materials extensively investigated in recent decades, polymorphs based on titanium (Ti), vanadium (V), zirconium (Zr), and niobium (Nb) are among the semiconductors that have aroused the interest of the scientific community and industry.^{14,15}

Among the above-reported elements, niobium is a transition metal with an atomic number of 41 and an atomic mass of 92.9064 u, exhibiting a body-centered cubic (BCC) structure, space group of O_h⁹, and density of 8.57 g cm⁻³. It has melting and boiling points of 2477 and 4744 °C, respectively, and acts as a superconductor at critical temperatures below 9.3 K.¹⁶ Niobium-based alloys exhibit high corrosion resistance, biocompatibility, low densities, and good ductility at room temperature.¹⁷

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Figure 1. Schematic representation for HEBM synthesis of CaNb_2O_6 , where (a) weighing of precursors and spheres (balls), (b) the milling process, (c) reaction involved and different synthesis time to obtain the samples BaNb_x , where $x = 0.5, 1, 3,$ and 4 h, and (d) characterization techniques used in this study.

Niobium compounds such as oxides, nitrides, carbides, and borates are interesting materials for several applications, including energy storage, catalysis, antimicrobial, and water splitting.¹⁸ Introducing rare-earth ions can modify their properties, creating materials that exhibit optical properties as efficient visible or infrared light.¹⁹

Recent studies have been focused on the synthesis and application of niobates with perovskite-like structures (ABO_3 or AB_2O_6). Among others, barium niobate (BaNb_2O_6) is a well-known semiconductor that exhibits high stability and interesting optical properties that can be used in high-capacitance electronic devices, piezoelectric materials, and catalysts.^{18,20–22}

Several synthesis methods have been adopted in the synthesis of BaNb_2O_6 . Singh et al.,²³ carried out the production of BaNb_2O_6 nanoparticles using the sol–gel method, starting with barium chloride (BaCl_2) and niobium pentoxide (Nb_2O_5) solubilized in hydrofluoric acid (HF) for 16 h. This was followed by thermal treatment, giving samples at a temperature of 1125 °C for 4 h. On the other hand, the study reported by Dudhe et al.,²⁰ carried out a synthesis and study of the ferroelectric properties of BaNb_2O_6 nanoparticles synthesized using the thermal treatment method, initially at 600 and 650 °C for 6 h, followed by a new heat treatment at 850 °C for 6 h. Meanwhile, Jana et al.²⁴ obtained barium niobate nanoparticles doped with praseodymium ions (Pr^{3+}), using the conventional solid-state method, starting from barium carbonate and niobium pentoxide, under thermal treatment at a temperature of 1200 °C for 5 h. Therefore, in the main part, two studies reported that obtaining these materials involved only long reaction periods, strongly acidic reagents, and high temperatures, which are poor economic and environmental aspects.

However, high temperature, a long synthesis period, and addition of surfactants or organic solvents are the main disadvantages of chemical synthesis. In this context, the high-energy ball milling (HEBM) method is a promising approach to obtaining high-entropy nanomaterials or semiconductors that crystallize at high temperatures. The direct synthesis by HEBM reduces the synthesis time, which can adopt oxides or carbonates as precursors of the solid-state synthesis.

Previously, Nascimento, et al.²⁵ reported the obtention of a Rynersonite-like structure of CaNb_2O_6 through the HEBM, reducing the temperature of crystallization from 1440 °C to

room temperature, as also, the dependence of several steps in the chemical synthesis by hydrothermal or coprecipitation assisted by thermal treatment. This confirms the ecofriendly and cost-effective approach to obtaining materials that are usually dependent on the long period of synthesis, as well as the high temperature of crystallization.

This innovative study successfully synthesized bare BaNb_2O_6 using the HEBM method at room temperature. Therefore, the sample prepared for 3 h (BaNb_3) and 4 h (BaNb_4) was systematically investigated through structural Rietveld refinement, Raman spectroscopy, diffuse reflectance, scanning electron microscopy, and electrochemical analysis by cyclic voltammetry.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials. Barium carbonate (BaCO_3 , purity of >99.95%) and niobium pentoxide (Nb_2O_5 , purity of >99.99%), potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) trihydrate ($\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$), purity of >99.95%), potassium chloride (KCl, purity of >99%), *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{NO}$, purity of >99.5%), and poly(vinylidene fluoride) ($(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{F}_2)_n$, Mw \approx 534 000), were purchased by Sigma–Aldrich. For barium carbonate and niobium pentoxide, the particle size was less than 40 nm, and they were used without any prior treatment.

2.2. HEBM Synthesis. BaNb_2O_6 was synthesized using high-energy ball-milling equipment (Spex, Model 8000 M Mixer Mill). The stoichiometric amounts of BaCO_3 (0.9422 g) and Nb_2O_5 (1.2685 g) were introduced into a stainless steel reactor (50 mL capacity) with 42.8534g of stainless steel balls, which six of these balls had 10 mm diameter balls (523.59 mm³) and eight of them, with 5 mm diameter balls (65.45 mm³), resulting in a ball-to-powder ratio (BPR) of 18.5:1. The samples were prepared and analyzed after the milling time synthesis of 0.5, 1, 2, 3, and 4 h, which are identified as $\text{BaNb}_{0.5}$, BaNb_1 , BaNb_2 , BaNb_3 and BaNb_4 , respectively. The synthesis evolution was conducted by X-ray diffraction until formation of the structure occurred. The schematic representation available in Figures 1a–d summarizes the steps adopted in the synthesis of all samples.

2.3. Characterization. The crystal structure of the prepared materials was analyzed by using the X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique. The XRD data were recorded on a conventional Bruker diffractometer, D2Phaser, with Cu radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$), 2θ range from 10 to 80°, step size

Figure 2. (a) Diffraction pattern of the BaNb_0.5h, BaNb_1h, BaNb_2h, BaNb_3h, and BaNb_4h samples, (b, c) Rietveld refinement plot performed for the BaNb_3h and BaNb_4h samples, and (d) representation for the unit cell of barium niobate by performed Rietveld refinement results.

of 0.02° , and rotation speed set at 15 rpm. The XRD data were structurally refined using the Rietveld method, using publicly available Fullprof software (utilized January 20, 2024). Among other parameters, we refined the lattice parameters (a , b , c , α , β , and γ), atomic coordinates, occupancy (O_{cc}), isotropic thermal factor (B_{iso}), background, and the parameters U , V , W , IG , X , and Y , from the Thompson–Cox–Hastings pseudo-Voigt axial asymmetry and divergence function.

The active symmetry modes of the prepared samples were examined using Raman spectroscopy, conducted with a BWtek i-Raman plus spectrometer in the range of 50 to 4000 cm^{-1} . To acquire the Raman spectrum, an 85% power laser with a wavelength of excitation at 523 nm was adopted, with under 15 000 accumulations and an integration time of 15 s.

The optical bandgap energy (E_{gap}) of BaNb_2O_6 was determined through UV-vis spectroscopy using diffuse reflectance (UV-vis/DRS). The UV-vis/DRS spectrum was acquired by a Shimadzu UV-2600 UV-vis spectrophotometer, collecting the reflectance ($R\%$) from 200 to 1000 nm, where the barium sulfate (BaSO_4) was used as the internal reflectance standard.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) images of all matrix elements were collected using a VEGA3 TESCAN microscope. Before obtaining SEM images, 10 mg of the sample was dispersed in acetone using the ultrasonic washing machine for 5 min. Subsequently, 0.5 mL of

the suspension was collected and added drop by drop to the aluminum holder.

The electrochemistry study by cyclic voltammetry (CV) was performed using an Autolab potentiostat, a PGSTAT 204. Initially, the modified glass carbon as a working electrode was prepared using 0.2 g of BaNb_2O_6 , 0.01 g of black carbon, and 0.01 g of poly(vinylidene fluoride) polymer (PVDF), solubilized in 1 mL of *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone for 3 h under magnetic stirring. Then, the suspension was deposited over a fluorine tin oxide-coated glass slide (SnO_2/F , surface resistivity $\approx 7\ \Omega/\text{sq}$) in a surface area of 1 cm^2 , which was dried at a planar surface of a magnetic stirring plate for 6 h at a temperature of $55\ ^\circ\text{C}$. The CV curves were collected using silver/silver chloride as the standard electrode and platinum as a counter electrode, as well as the solution of potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) and potassium chloride at concentrations of 1 mol^{-1} and 5 mmolL^{-1} , respectively.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 2a–d illustrate the diffraction pattern of the precursors (BaCO_3 and Nb_2O_5) and samples milled at times of 0.5, 1, 2, 3, and 4 h. Additionally, the Rietveld refinement plots for the BaNb_3h and BaNb_4h samples and the schematic representation of the unit cell of the BaNb_3h sample.

In Figure 2a, it can be observed that the physical mixture shows the crystallographic planes characteristic of barium carbonate, which exhibits the orthorhombic structure and

Figure 3. (a) Raman spectrum of BaNb_2O_6 (experimental) and (b) deconvoluted Raman spectrum of BaNb_2O_6 of the 3 h sample.

space group of $Pm\bar{c}n$, with lattice parameters of $a = 5.3140 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 8.9040 \text{ \AA}$, and $c = 6.4300 \text{ \AA}$. These values agree with the crystallographic data in the Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (ICSD) Card No. 15196. On the other hand, the remaining diffraction planes were indexed as niobium oxide polymorphs. Therefore, the monoclinic phase (Nb_2O_5) with a space group of $P12/m1$ is indexed as ICSD Card No. 000029. The second phase was indexed for niobium oxide with the formula $\text{Nb}_{12}\text{O}_{29}$ and space group $A12/a1$, according to the ICSD Card No. 24111. The evolution of milling time led to the modification of characteristic crystallographic planes of niobium pentoxide and barium carbonate, indicating the formation of BaNb_2O_6 . These findings agree with the crystallographic information available in ICSD Card No. 39320 and the literature.²⁶ Based on Figure 1a, it is noted that the evolution of the synthesis time led to a decrease in the intensity of the characteristic crystallographic planes of the niobium pentoxide polymorphs, as well as the characteristics of the barium carbonate structure, until total disappearance occurred, as shown in the XRD pattern of the BaNb_3h sample. After 3 h of synthesis, it was observed that there were no significant variations in the intensity of the diffraction peaks when compared with the diffraction pattern collected for the BaNb_3h sample. Furthermore, the intensity and profile of the diffraction peaks obtained for the sample synthesized in BaNb_3h indicate the formation of materials with high crystallinity degrees and reduced crystallite size, typical of nanomaterials.

In this study, the structural refinement of the BaNb_3h and BaNb_4h samples was performed using the Rietveld method,²⁷ using the crystallographic information from ICSD Card No. 39320 as input theoretical data.

The structural information collected through the Rietveld refinement study, such as lattice parameters, atomic coordinates (x , y , and z), unit-cell volume, and occupancy (Occ), is summarized in Table S1 in the Electronic Supporting Information. Therefore, based on the Rietveld refinement analysis, we confirmed the bare phase as an orthorhombic structure with a space group of $C2221$, well indeed for samples prepared after 3 h and 4 h. Moreover, the computed data

reveals lattice parameters of $a = 7.849(3) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 12.208(8) \text{ \AA}$, and $c = 10.291(8) \text{ \AA}$ for sample BaNb_3h , while sample BaNb_4h exhibits lattice parameters of $a = 7.847(3) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 12.210(1) \text{ \AA}$, and $c = 10.289(9) \text{ \AA}$. Therefore, it can be seen that the a - and c -axes show a reduction of 0.02% and 0.01%, respectively, while the b -axis increases by 0.01%, for an increase in the synthesis time of 3 h to 4 h. The respective unit-cell volumes for the BaNb_3h and BaNb_4h samples were $986.271(1)$ and $985.936(2) \text{ \AA}^3$, indicating a 0.03% reduction in the unit-cell volume.

The representation of the unit cell using the Visualization Electronic and Structural Analysis (VESTA) software enabled the identification that the unit cell of BaNb_2O_6 has distorted $[\text{NbO}_6]$ clusters of octahedral symmetry, in which all Nb–O bonds exhibit different bond lengths and angles between atoms. Meanwhile, the barium atoms are coordinated with ten oxygen atoms, resulting in distorted $[\text{BaO}_{10}]$ and $[\text{BaO}_8]$ clusters. The complementary study about the bond length for BaNb_3h sample is presented in Figure S1 in the Electronic Supporting Information, where different bond lengths for Ba–O and Nb–O are noticed in their respective clusters due to the structural defects, oxygen vacancies, and microstrain introduced by the high energy ball milling method. The average crystallite size was calculated using the Scherrer method,²⁸ where crystallite sizes of 22.12 and 20.48 nm were found for the BaNb_3h and BaNb_4h samples, respectively.

Figure 3a shows the Raman spectra of $\text{BaNb}_0.5\text{h}$, BaNb_1h , BaNb_2h , BaNb_3h , and BaNb_4h samples, as well as the Raman spectrum of precursors (Nb_2O_5 and BaCO_3) in the spectral range from 80 to 1000 cm^{-1} . The deconvoluted spectrum of the BaNb_3h sample is shown in Figure 3b.

Initially, the vibrational Raman spectrum collected for barium carbonate, which has a space group of $Pm\bar{m}n$, shows seven vibrational bands at 132, 147, 176, 219, 690, 889, and 1056 cm^{-1} , which are very close to those reported in the literature.²⁹ The bands in the spectral range from 80 to 219 cm^{-1} are associated with the external active modes of the structure, while the bands at 690, 889, and 1056 cm^{-1} are attributed to the respective B_{2g} , B_{2g} , and A_g active modes. On

Figure 4. Optical bandgap of (a) BaNb_{0.5}, (b) BaNb₁, (c) BaNb₂, (d) BaNb₃, (e) BaNb₄, and (f) the E_{gap} values against ball milling synthesis time.

the other hand, the vibrational Raman spectrum of Nb₂O₅ precursor collected in this study shows 11 bands at 174, 233, 256, 303, 464, 542, 620, 663, 831, 894, and 992 cm⁻¹; these are all very similar to those reported by Jehng and Wachs,³⁰ for bulk for Nb₂O₅, heated at 1000 °C. In addition, these authors declare the occurrence of a phase mixture of monoclinic and orthorhombic structures of Nb₂O₅ in this respective studied sample.

The obtention of orthorhombic structure characteristic of BaNb₂O₆, with a space group of C2221, is confirmed by Raman spectroscopy, following XRD and Rietveld refinement analysis, as reported above. Based on Figure 3a, the exposure of precursors to high-energy ball milling synthesis induces the continuous decrease of active Raman bands for CaCO₃ and

Nb₂O₅. In contrast, the intensity of bands located at 137, 185, 211, 256, 280, 336, 394, 426, 458, and 668 cm⁻¹ is continuously increased until 4 h of synthesis. The vibrational mode, with the highest intensity at 668 cm⁻¹, agrees with the spectra of BaNb₂O₆ ceramics with an orthorhombic structure reported by Ke et al.³¹ Moreover, it is confirmed that the synthesis time of 3 h is enough to obtain the pure phase of BaNb₂O₆, as also reported in the XRD analysis.

The complementary study of the Raman spectrum regarding the vibrational modes contained in the Raman vibrational spectrum for the BaNb₃ sample was performed by deconvolution. In this study, public-domain Fityk software was used. In the adjustment, a Gaussian function was

Figure 5. SEM images and EDX spectrum of (a, b) BaNb_{0.5}, (c, d) BaNb₁, (e, f) BaNb₂, (g, h) BaNb₃, and (i, j) BaNb₄ samples.

computed for the intensity and width of the bands, and the error rate was less than 5%.

As can be seen in Figure 3b, 22 Gaussian curves were obtained for theoretical fitting using the experimental spectrum of the BaNb₃ sample. According to the study reported by Repelin, Husson, and Brusset,³² BaNb₂O₆ exhibits, according to group theory, the general formula presented in eq 1 for optical modes:

$$\Gamma_{\text{opt}} = 8A_g + 8B_{1g} + 5B_{2g} + 3B_{3g} + 4A_u + 5B_{1u} + 9B_{2u} + 9B_{3u} \quad (1)$$

However, the 4A_u modes are inactive in vibrational Raman and infrared spectroscopy. The 8A_g, 8B_{1g}, 5B_{2g}, and 3B_{3g} modes are inactive in Raman spectroscopy; nevertheless, according to the authors, the A_g, B_{1g}, and B_{3g} modes do not exist, resulting in 21 active modes that can be identified in the characteristic spectrum of the structure of barium niobate for the point group D_{2h}, according to the irreducible formula presented in eq 2:

$$\Gamma_{\text{Raman}} = 7A_g + 7B_{1g} + 4B_{2g} + 3B_{3g} \quad (2)$$

For the remaining modes, that is, 5B_{1u}, 9B_{2u}, and 9B_{3u}, 19 active vibrational modes are expected in IR spectroscopy, reduced by the lack of a B_{1u} mode, two B_{2u} modes, and a B_{3u} mode, ultimately obtaining the irreducible formula presented in eq 3:

$$\Gamma_{\text{IR}} = 4B_{1u} + 7B_{2u} + 8B_{3u} \quad (3)$$

The deconvolution of the experimental spectrum of the BaNb₃ sample, as shown in Figure 3b, made it possible to identify 22 Gaussians, which adjusted to the bands contained in the vibrational spectrum. Therefore, it is noted that the band of strong intensity located at 712 cm⁻¹, attributed to the B_{1g} mode, is associated with the stretching movements of the Nb–O bonds located in the [NbO₆] clusters of octahedral symmetry. For the deconvoluted spectrum, five bands were obtained in the range between 550 and 800 cm⁻¹, suggesting the existence of deformations of the Nb–O bonds, as well as Ba–O, leading to the coupling of secondary vibrations and the occurrence of oxygen vacancies and structural defects at short and long range. Similarly, other bands of weak intensity, mainly between 80 and 500 cm⁻¹, were identified, in addition to the position of the modes reported by the authors,³² which are related to the movements of the crystalline lattice. Bearing in mind that the authors carried out the heat treatment of the studied samples at 1200 °C for 60 h, it is possible that they eliminated most of the crystalline defects, ultimately obtaining a material with a high degree of ordering with the absence or low density of vacancies and crystalline distortions.

The optical bandgap (E_{gap}) of all studied samples was obtained by UV-vis by diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (UV-vis/DRS), as seen in Figures 4a–f. Initially, the values of the Kubelka–Munk function were obtained by adopting direct allowed transitions, specifically with $n = 0.5$.³³ Subsequently, the wavelength values were converted to photon energy, using the equation $E_{\text{phot}} = 1240/\lambda$, where λ represents the wavelength. Finally, the E_{gap} parameter was determined by extrapolating the linear section of the curve to plot the values of the Kubelka–Munk function $[(F(R_{\infty})h\nu)^2]$ against E_{phot} .³⁴

Based on the results (Figures 4a–f), the lower E_{gap} (3.45 eV), was obtained for the synthesis time of 30 min, which is attributed to the characteristic of niobium pentoxide (Nb₂O₅),

one that at this synthesis time, the amount of BaNb₂O₆ was negligible, corroborating with the XRD analysis. Therefore, there was a good agreement with the reported E_{gap} by Ai and Xiong,³⁵ where niobium pentoxide was prepared using the dual deposition method under silicon substrates. In addition, it was verified that the increase of synthesis time conduces to different E_{gap} values, which were 3.52 eV (BaNb₁), 3.82 eV (BaNb₂), 3.77 eV (BaNb₃), and 3.84 eV, for BaNb₄. As shown in Figure 4f, a nonlinear profile for correlation of the synthesis time with the optical bandgap value suggests that phase composition, crystallite size, and structural defects are the main involved factors. Therefore, these optical band gaps are characteristics of inorganic semiconductors with pronounced photon absorption in the spectrum's ultraviolet region (UVA). For BaNb₂O₆ the valence band (VB) is predominantly composed of O 2p orbitals, while the conduction band (CB) is mostly composed of Nb 4d orbitals.¹⁸

The scanning electron microscopy images (SEM) and dispersive energy X-ray diffraction (EDX) images are presented in Figures 5a–j. Thus, the SEM images of all prepared samples are shown in Figures 5a, 5c, 5e, 5g, and 5i, which are respectively associated with the BaNb_{0.5}, BaNb₁, BaNb₂, BaNb₃, and BaNb₄. For all cases, the occurrence of aggregate microcrystals with heterogeneous dimensions and format was identified, as well as the crystals with submicrometer dimensions, these morphologies being characteristic of materials prepared using the high-energy milling method without heat treatment. Bentes et al.³⁶ report the synthesis and characterization of SnWO₄ microcrystals using the high-energy milling method, where the morphological change of the precursors is verified, increasing the synthesis time. The authors describe the occurrence of friction energy, inducing phase conversion and crystallization of SnWO₄ samples.

The semiquantitative analysis, as can be seen in the EDX spectrum (Figures 5b, 5d, 5f, 5h, and 5j), confirmed the high purity of the synthesized sample. The elements identified were niobium (Nb), barium (Ba), and oxygen (O). The carbon EDX peak is attributed to the carbon tape used in the deposition of samples over the stubs before the SEM and EDX spectrum.

The atomic percentages of the elements identified in the EDX spectra acquisition are presented in Figures 5b, 5d, 5f, 5h, and 5j, where the peaks associated with the Nb elements, associated with the L α and L β_1 lines, were identified near 2.17 and 2.26 keV, respectively. The dispersive energy peaks for barium were observed near 4.46, 4.6, and 4.9 keV, associated with the L α , L β_1 , and L β_2 lines, respectively. For the oxygen atom, the electronic transitions are attributed to the K α and K β lines, which are near 0.523 and 0.532 keV, respectively, which is observed as a single peak.

The ratio Nb/Ba (mol/mol) resulted in 1.88 for the sample BaNb_{0.5} and 1.93 for the BaNb₁ sample, while, after 1 h of synthesis time, the ratio Nb/Ba was near 2.0 for samples BaNb₂, BaNb₃, and BaNb₄. These results agree with the study carried out by X-ray diffraction and structural refinement by the Rietveld method, which indicates the formation of structures with a chemical formula close to BaNb₂O₆. These differences for BaNb_{0.5} and BaNb₁ samples indicate the phase mixture of Nb₂O₅, CaCO₃ and CaNb₂O₆ compounds. Therefore, the vibrational Raman profile, as well as the information obtained by diffuse reflectance, is influenced by

Figure 6. Cyclic voltammograms obtained for (a) all electrodes made as previously prepared and with glassy carbon only at a scan rate of 100 mVs^{-1} in the potential range of -0.3 V to 0.9 V , and (b–f) CV curves in the range of 1 mVs^{-1} to 100 mVs^{-1} for samples BaNb_{0.5} (panel (b)), BaNb₁ (panel (c)), BaNb₂ (panel (d)), BaNb₃ (panel (e)), and BaNb₄ (panel (f)).

structural defects, oxygen vacancies, crystallite size, and composition of crystalline phases.

There is a discrepancy concerning the expected value for the percentages associated with oxygen, which is related to the thickness of the sample analyzed, the efficiency of the vacuum system in the acquisition of EDX spectra, the porosity of the samples and the diffusion capacity carbon dioxide and oxygen, by the analyzed samples.^{37,38}

The investigation of the electrochemical properties of all prepared samples was carried out via cyclic voltammetry (CV),^{39–41} using the electrochemical probe composed of the redox pair ($\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$) formed by potassium ferrocyanide, as seen in Figures 6a–f.

In this study, the working electrode was prepared from a paste containing glassy carbon/black carbon, active material (BaNb_2O_6), and the PVDF polymer in a ratio 90:5:5 (wt/wt/wt). The paste was dispersed in NMP solvent and then deposited on an FTO substrate with a geometric area of 1 cm^2 .

Based on Figure 6a, the electrodes prepared using the synthesized samples as active material result in no increase in the electrochemical properties, obtaining the best responses for the intensity of two peaks, that is, cathodic and anodic peaks, for sample BaNb₄ (Figure 6f). In this case, $438.06 \mu\text{A}$ ($V = 0.29 \text{ V}$) for the anodic peak, and $431.61 \mu\text{A}$ ($V = 0.16 \text{ V}$) for the cathodic peak, at scan rate of 100 mVs^{-1} , the lower sensitivity was observed for sample BaNb_{0.5} (Figure 6b), which also showed displacement for the cathodic and anodic

Figure 7. Current versus square root of scan rate plot for cathodic and anodic peaks of electrodes containing samples (a) BaNb_{0.5}, (b) BaNb₁, (c) BaNb₂, (d) BaNb₃, and (e) BaNb₄. (f) Specific capacitance for scan rate from 1 to 100 mV s⁻¹ of all samples.

peaks, for potential values of 0.52 V and -0.11 V, for the cathodic and anodic peaks, respectively. For comparison purposes, an electrode containing only carbon and PVDF polymer was prepared, which showed an electrochemical profile with a low sensitivity for the redox pair. This profile is associated with the presence of a phase mixture, which results in modifications of the oxidative and reducing processes. Furthermore, it has been suggested that the increase in synthesis time contributes to the mixture of two precursor oxides and the evolution to the formation of the crystalline phase, as previously discussed in the analysis by X-ray diffraction and Raman spectroscopy.

From the cyclic voltammetry data, in this case, using the current values obtained for the cathodic and anodic peaks for the scan speed range from 10 mV s⁻¹ to 100 mV s⁻¹, it was possible to plot the graph of current versus the square of scan rate (ν^2), obtaining the linearized data as presented in Figures 7a–e. Therefore, it is possible to note that, for all the prepared samples, the linearity of the current intensity is noted with the increase in the scan speed, where, for the BaNb_{0.5} and BaNb₃ samples, the voltammetric profile, as presented in Figures 6b and 6e, indicates an almost reversible profile, which reflects in the variation in current intensity and shift of the potential values, observed for the oxidation and reduction processes of the electrochemical probe.

Table 1. Specific Capacitance (C_p), Electrolyte, and Experimental Conditions of Electrodes Prepared with BaNb_0.5, BaNb_1, BaNb_2, BaNb_3, and BaNb_4, as Reported by the Literature

material	electrolyte	experimental conditions	C_p (mF cm ⁻²)	ref
BaNb_0.5	KCl 1 mol L ⁻¹	1 mV s ⁻¹ / -0.3 to 0.9 V	694.30	this work
BaNb_1	KCl 1 mol L ⁻¹	1 mV s ⁻¹ / -0.3 to 0.9 V	1064.60	this work
BaNb_2	KCl 1 mol L ⁻¹	1 mV s ⁻¹ / -0.3 to 0.9 V	919.67	this work
BaNb_3	KCl 1 mol L ⁻¹	1 mV s ⁻¹ / -0.3 to 0.9 V	3375.66	this work
BaNb_4	KCl 1 mol L ⁻¹	1 mV s ⁻¹ / -0.3 to 0.9 V	280.33	this work
SWNT/WO ₃ /PANI	LiCl ₄ 0.1 mol L ⁻¹	50 mV s ⁻¹ / -0.6 to 0.9 V	28.5	43
WO ₃ /PANI	H ₂ SO ₄ 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	100 mV s ⁻¹ / 0 to 1 V	147.8	44
GF/PANI/PEDOT:PSS	KCl 3 mol L ⁻¹	50 mV s ⁻¹ / -0.2 to 0.8 V	2600	45
MOF/PANI	CH ₃ COOH 0.1 mol L ⁻¹	50 mV s ⁻¹ / -1.0 to -0.2 V	2.1	46

Figure 8. Mott–Schottky plots for (a) BaNb_0.5, (b) BaNb_1, (c) BaNb_2, (d) BaNb_3, (e) BaNb_4, and (f) E_{fb} versus synthesis time in the preparation of samples.

The specific capacitance of the electrodes was calculated using eq 6,⁴² where the ACV corresponds to the area of the

curve obtained for cyclic voltammetry obtained for different scan rates (ν). In this study, the interval of scan rate was 1 mV

s^{-1} to 100 mV s^{-1} . Meanwhile, m is the mass of the active material in the electrodes and $(V_1 - V_2)$ is the potential window used to collect the cyclic voltammetry data, which is between 0.9 V and -0.3 V.

$$C_p = \frac{A_{CV}}{2m\nu(V_1 - V_2)} \quad (4)$$

The curve profile for the specific capacitance values, as a function of the scan rate, is presented in Figure 7f, where the specific capacitance values for all samples decrease with the increase in the scanning speed caused by the low separation of charges due to the high speed at which the diffusion and charge transfer processes occur throughout the solution and electrode surface. The highest specific capacitance values were obtained for the BaNb_3 sample—in this case, $3375.66 \text{ mF cm}^{-2}$ —while the lowest specific capacitance was obtained for the BaNb_4 sample, corresponding to $280.33 \text{ mF cm}^{-2}$. Table 1 is available for the specific capacitance and experimental conditions reported in this study and adopted by the literature.

Figures 8a–f present the Mott–Schottky plots⁴⁷ obtained for the potential range from -1 V to 1 V, adopting the model presented in eq 5.

$$\frac{1}{C_{SC^2}} = \frac{2}{\epsilon\epsilon_0 A^2 N d} \left(V - V_{fb} - \frac{k_B T}{e} \right) \quad (5)$$

Here, e is the electronic charge ($1.60 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$), ϵ the relative permittivity of the p -type metal-oxide-semiconductor thin-film, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, A the exposed surface area, k_B the Boltzmann constant ($1.38 \times 10^{-23} \text{ m}^2 \text{ kg s}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$), and T the temperature (in Kelvin).

Therefore, the value of the flat band (E_{fb}) was obtained from the values $\frac{1}{C_{SC^2}}$ versus potential (V) when adopting the value of $y = 0$ for the equation obtained for the extrapolation of the straight section of the curve. Thus, the space-charge capacitance (C_{SC}) varies as a function of the applied potential for the analyzed semiconductors. In this case, the positive slope for the obtained equation indicates semiconductor materials with electron-donating properties, that is, n -type semiconductors.⁴⁸ On the other hand, the negative slope indicates materials with hole-donating characteristics, that is, p -type semiconductors.⁴⁹

Based on the graphs obtained in Figures 8a–e, all materials obtained in this study have a hole-donating nature; that is, they are p -type semiconductors, where the BaNb_0.5 sample initially resulted in an E_{fb} value higher than that of the BaNb_1, BaNb_2, and BaNb_3 samples, which may be related to the phase composition, where Nb_2O_5 is an n -type semiconductor. Therefore, for p -type semiconductors, the Fermi energy is close to the conduction band, in this case, between 0.1 and 0.2 V, and the E_{fb} is below the conduction band but above the Fermi energy. This characteristic allows the search for p – n heterojunctions, which facilitate charge migration and, consequently, electronic properties that induce several semiconductor processes for technological applications.

In the study carried out by Wang et al.,⁵⁰ heterojunctions were obtained from the combination of $\text{SnO}_{2-x}/\text{BiOI}$ materials, which resulted in efficient performance in the photodegradation of the antibiotic tetracycline and the disinfection of pathogenic micro-organisms (in this case, strains of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria).

Based on the Mott–Schottky plots and the UV–vis by DRS spectroscopy, the band potentials for the valence band (E_{VB}) and conduction band (E_{CB}) were calculated using eqs 6 and 7, as demonstrated in Figure 9.

$$E_{VB} = \chi - E^e + 0.5E_{gap} \quad (6)$$

$$E_{CB} = E_{VB} - E_{gap} \quad (7)$$

Figure 9. Schematic representation of electron transfer in BaNb_2O_6 , for samples prepared at 3 h (BaNb_3) and 4 h (BaNb_4) of milling time.

Therefore, the E_{VB} and E_{CB} values for BaNb 3 are 3.15 eV and -0.62 eV, respectively. On the other hand, for sample BaNb 4, values of 3.19 eV for E_{VB} and -0.65 eV for E_{CB} were found. The E_{CB} and E_{VB} values indicate the broad capacity for forming oxidizing species in aqueous media by absorbing energy with a wavelength equal to or greater than the E_{gap} value of the synthesized semiconductors. This way, when adsorbing water molecules on its surface, the holes photogenerated by electrons ejected from the valence band to the conduction band oxidize the water molecules to H^+ and HO^- ions. On the other hand, the electrons excited to the conduction band are captured by oxygen molecules, reducing them to superoxide species ($\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$). In the study reported by Cho et al.³³ the synthesis of BaNb_2O_6 by the hydrothermal method shows an E_{gap} value of 3.54 eV with satisfactory photocatalytic performance under UV light in the discolorization of RhB dye solution.

Therefore, the materials synthesized in this study are promising for applications involving the decontamination of effluents containing persistent organic compounds. Thus, they become attractive candidates for the composition of p – n heterojunctions for photocatalytic applications.

4. CONCLUSION

In summary, the barium niobate sample, BaNb_2O_6 , was efficiently prepared using a high-energy ball milling method at room temperature for 3 and 4 h of synthesis. Structural analysis by Rietveld refinement and Raman vibrational spectroscopy confirm the successful synthesis of the BaNb_2O_6 structure with high purity and crystallinity. The obtained optical bandgap, $E_{gap} = 3.77$ and 3.84 eV for samples BaNb_3 and BaNb_4, respectively, is characteristic of semiconductors; in this case, the Mott–Schottky plot reveals a p -type semiconductor, which is an interesting material for applications such as photocatalysts or phosphor matrices.

Regarding the surface analysis and semiquantitative examination using scanning electron microscopy, various particles ranging in size from micrometers to submicrometers are observed, and the EDX peaks suggest the high purity of the sample. Finally, cyclic voltammetry curves indicate the reversible profile of the samples, which, for sample BaNb₃, results in a value of 3375.66 mF cm⁻².

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.iecr.4c02578>.

The bond length for [BaO_x], $x = 10$ and 8 , and [NbO₆] clusters of BaNb₃ and BaNb₄ samples by Rietveld refinement, and results for atomic coordinates (x , y , and z), wykko, site and occupation for samples BaNb₃, BaNb₄, and ICSD Card No. 39320 (PDF)

■ AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

José Fábio de Lima Nascimento – Graduate Program in Natural Resources Engineering in the Amazon, PRODERNA/ITEC/UFPA, Federal University of Pará, Belém, PA 66075-110, Brazil; Email: fabio_lima@ifam.edu.br

Francisco Xavier Nobre – Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Amazonas, Manaus, AM 69020-120, Brazil; Programa Multicêntrico de Pós-Graduação em Bioquímica e Biologia Molecular, Universidade do Estado do Amazonas, Escola Superior de Saúde, Manaus, AM 69065-001, Brazil; orcid.org/0000-0002-0883-3651; Email: francisco.nobre@ifam.edu.br

Authors

Yurimiler Leyet Ruiz – Departamento de Engenharia de Materiais, Laboratório de Processamento de Materiais Tecnológicos (LPMaT), Universidade Federal do Amazonas, Instituto de Ciências Exatas, Manaus 69067-005, Brazil; orcid.org/0000-0002-5774-5391

Otoniel da Cunha Mendes – FENTOMLAB, Universidade do Estado do Amazonas, Escola Superior de Tecnologia, Manaus, AM 69050-020, Brazil

Francisco Marcos Costa Batista – Catalonia Institute for Energy Research - IREC, 08930 Barcelona, Spain; Department of Inorganic & Organic Chemistry, Universitat de Barcelona, 08028 Barcelona, Spain

Andreu Cabot – Catalonia Institute for Energy Research - IREC, 08930 Barcelona, Spain; Department of Inorganic & Organic Chemistry, Universitat de Barcelona, 08028 Barcelona, Spain; orcid.org/0000-0002-7533-3251

José Milton Elias de Matos – Programa de Pós-Graduação em Química, Centro de Ciências da Natureza (CCN), Universidade Federal do Piauí, Teresina 64049-550, Brazil; orcid.org/0000-0003-3476-399X

Robson Dantas Ferreira – Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Amazonas, Manaus, AM 69020-120, Brazil

Marcus Valério Botelho do Nascimento – Post-graduate Program of Chemistry, Federal University of Amazonas (UFAM), Instituto de Ciências Exatas, Manaus 69067-005, Brazil; orcid.org/0000-0002-5376-5643

Libertamar Bilhalva Saraiva – Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Amazonas, Manaus, AM 69020-120, Brazil

João Nazareno Nonato Quaresma – Graduate Program in Natural Resources Engineering in the Amazon, PRODERNA/ITEC/UFPA, Federal University of Pará, Belém, PA 66075-110, Brazil; orcid.org/0000-0001-9365-7498

Complete contact information is available at: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.iecr.4c02578>

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Notes

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